

The new record invasive alien species (IAS) *Zelus renardii* (Kolenati, 1857) (Hemiptera: Heteroptera: Reduviidae) in central Anatolia (Turkey)

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ABSTRACT: In this paper, new distribution record of the invasive species *Zelus renardii* (Kolenati, 1857) in Turkey is given after four years of its introduction to Turkey.

After the first records of *Zelus renardii* (Kolenati, 1857) from İzmir and Istanbul provinces in Turkey in 2016 (Çerçi & Koçak, 2016), the species has been recorded from Ankara province (in central anatolia) as a first record in this study.

With this new record, the distribution area also shows the eastward enlarging of the species in the Anatolian Peninsula.

KEYWORDS: Heteroptera, Reduviidae, *Zelus renardii*, alien, invasive species (IAS), expansion, fauna, central Anatolia, Ankara, Turkey

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INTRODUCTION

Species of Reduviidae are predator taxa, and are a large Heteropteran family and including seven thousand species worldwide (Henry, 2009).

According to reviewed literatures (Zhang et al. 2016) *Zelus* Fabricius, 1803 is a reduviid genus in the subfamily Harpactorinae, and

Zelus is endemic to and widely distributed throughout the New World, ranging from southern Canada through central Argentina.

Zelus renardii (Kolenati, 1857) is known as “leafhopper assassin bug” native of Central and North America. Introduced in several countries across the World.

The species *Zelus renardii* (Kolenati, 1857)

has previously been recorded in several countries in North and South America and Europe.

Z. renardii (Kolenati, 1857) has been to date recorded in some countries in Europa. Invasion of this species in Europa was reported for the first time from Greece by Davranoglou (2011) and Petrakis & Moulet (2011).

In the year 2012, the species was given in Spain by Baena & Torres (2012), Vivas (2012), Goala et al (2019). It was reported in Italy in 2013-2014 by Dioli (2013) and Cornara et al. (2014).

In the years 2014 and 2015, it was recorded Crete Island (Daniels 2014, Roditakis 2014, van der Heyden, 2015).

In the year 2017 it was found in Albania by van der Heyden (2017) and in the year 2018 was found in Israel (van der Heyden, 2018).

In the year 2019, it was found in France

by Garrouste (2019).

In Turkey, it was found in 2015 and 2016 in two provinces Izmir and Istanbul by Çerçi & Koçak (2016). This invasion of this species in the Central Anatolian Region has not recorded until this date. According to some literature have been recorded this species in urban areas, gardens, parks and inhabited places in Europa (Davranoglou, 2011; Petrakis & Moulet, 2011; Simov et al., 2017, Goula et al., 2019).

MATERIALS AND METHODS

This study was conducted in Ankara province in Central Anatolia Region of Turkey. Two male specimen of this species were collected from a locations in the study area in 2020.

The specimen were collected with sweep net on the herbaceous vegetation. Specimens are deposited in the Gazi University Zoological Museum (ZMGU) collection.

Figure 1. The records of *Zelus renardii* (Kolenati, 1857) in Turkey. The colour in the circles indicate the order of the historical and new records. Red and blue circles show the recent record, black circles show new record.

Figure 2. Specimen of *Zelus renardii* (Kolenati, 1857). A. Dorsal view, B. Ventral view

Figure 3. Habitat and collected area of specimens of *Zelus renardii* (Kolenati, 1857)

RESULTS

Reduviidae Latreille, 1807

Harpactorinae Amyot & Serville, 1843

Zelus Fabricius, 1803

***Zelus renardii* (Kolenati, 1857)** (Figure 2 A–B)

Habitat:

The individual specimens of this species were found in the urban area. The vegetation of this area are; trees such as *Pinus nigra*, *Juniperus foetidissima*, *Cedrus libani*, *Populus* sp., *Salix babylonica*, *Eleagnus angustifolia*, *Armeniaca vulgaris*, *Tilia* sp., *Prunus* sp., also shrubs and herbaceous plants.

Material Examined:

Turkey: Ankara: town center, (39°58'25" N, 32°38'22"E), 20.IV.2020, 2 ♂♂, 835m, S. Kiyak leg. & det. (Figure 2) in an urban and anthropic environment (Figure 3).

Distribution in Turkey:

İstanbul: Esenyurt, İzmir: Urla (Çerçi & Koçak, 2016); Ankara (in this study)

Distribution in World:

North-Central-South America: Western and Southwestern USA, Mexico, El Salvador, Guatemala, Honduras, the Polynesian islands (Samoa, Hawaii), Jamaica, Philippines, Argentina and Chile. **Europe:** Albania, Greece (including Crete), France, Italy, Spain and, Turkey (European part). **Asia:** Israel, Turkey (Asian part) (van der Heyden 2015, 2017, 2018; Davranoglou, 2011; Petrakis & Moulet, 2011; Baena & Torres, 2012; Vivas, 2012; Aukema et al., 2013; Dioli, 2013; Cornara et al., 2014; Daniels, 2014; Goula et al., 2013; 2019; Roditakis, 2014; Zhang et al., 2016; Goula & Mata, 2015; Çerçi & Koçak, 2016; Simov et al., 2017; Rodríguez et al., 2018; D'Hervé et al., 2018; Pinzari, 2018; Garrouste, 2019).

CONCLUSION AND DISCUSSION

In the Turkey reduviid fauna, around 58 species have been recorded (Dursun &

Salur, 2013; Dursun, 2016; Çerçi & Koçak, 2016).

In this study, the first registration of the reduviid species *Z. renardii* (Kolenati, 1857) from Ankara province in the Central Anatolian Region was given. It is also shown and discussed of this species in Turkey and worldwide distribution.

Z. renardii (Kolenati, 1857 is enlarged from North and Central America (is native area), to South America, the Pacific Region and the Mediterranean Basin (Weirauch et al., 2012; Aukema et al., 2013; Zhang et al., 2016)

The first records of *Z. renardii* (Kolenati, 1857) in Turkey is reported in 2016 in the west of the Anatolia, Aegean Region (province: İzmir) and Marmara Region (province: Istanbul).

Invasion of *Z. renardii* (Kolenati, 1857) in Anatolian Peninsula and Thrace part of Turkey: Until this study, this species has been limited expansion in the Marmara and Aegean Regions of Turkey, and its distribution area is limited to the coastal regions only in the western and northwestern Anatolia. After first records from Turkey (Çerçi & Koçak, 2016) the species has not been mentioned until this present manuscript. (Figure 1).

The invasiv species *Z. renardii* (Kolenati, 1857) in the four years since it was detected for the first time in Turkey, has extended to the eastwards, around 500-600 km, and in this paper were reported two specimens this species recorded in Ankara city (Central Anatolia). *Z. renardii* (Kolenati, 1857) have been seems an gradually expanding species in Turkey (Figure 1).

Known locations of this species are limited to urban areas. According to literatures this species is found in different habitats, urban areas and agricultural areas in which it can reach high densities (Weyrauch et al., 2012). *Z. renardii* has been reported in urban, periurban and natural habitats in Europa. In the urban habitat, it may be found in private balconies, in streets with rows of trees, in small

green areas, in public vegetable gardens or in parks. *Zelus renardii* frequents also mixed orchards (peach trees, critics, apple trees, medlar trees, apricot trees), vegetable gardens next to natural semiarid scrublands and pinewoods, or abandoned cultivated lands with almond, olive and carob trees, now progressively covering with pines, aromatic plants and weeds. Natural habitats reported were scrublands and canes (Goula et al.,2019).

As can be seen from the literature given above in european countries, *Z. renardii* (Kolenati, 1857) has mainly being found in anthropic environments, either urban or agroecosystems, although some natural habitats have also been reported. Also in this paper has been observed and collected in urban and anthropic environment in Ankara (Turkey)(Figure 3).

Rodríguez Lozano et al. (2018) pointed out, the species could either be a sanitary concern due to biting to people and to large number of individuals in certain populations, or of importance as influencing foodwebs in agroecosystems or in nature.

The pathway of introduction for *Z. renardii* (Kolenati, 1857) in Turkey is uncertain, though it is most likely that the species was transported on exotic plants.

More research will be needed on the biology and ecology of *Z. renardii* (Kolenati, 1857) in Turkey.

As with all invasive species, its impact on natural fauna and flora its biology and ecology should be researched.

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